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Lifetime prediction of SteelCell[®] stacks using advanced multiphysics modelling

Ameir Mahgoub, Robert Leah, Duncan Gawel, Gavin Reade, Jack Howlett, Nick Lawrence, Subhasish Mukerjee, Mark Selby

Ceres Power Ltd.

Viking House, Foundry Lane, RH13 5PX Horsham/UK

Contact authors: www.EFCF.com/ContactRequest

Abstract

A major challenge in the development of SOFC stacks designed for long operating lives of the order of 50-100kh is predicting through-life performance without running durability tests under a particular set of operating conditions for 5-10 years. Whilst this is the final aim it is not practical for system design purposes or in the situation where product lifecycles are much longer than product development cycles. A particular challenge is that Ceres Power provides stack technology to multiple customers, most of whom have their own requirements for stack operating conditions, which means that degradation rates measured under one set of operating conditions are not necessarily directly applicable to a different set, and undertaking long term verification testing under every set of stack boundary conditions is not practical.

To address this issue, Ceres Power has invested significant effort into understanding mechanisms of performance degradation at the fundamental cell level, generating models of degradation as a function of time, temperature and current density. Most degradation mechanisms observed are common to all SOFC cells, such as poisoning of both electrodes and increases in ohmic resistance due to oxide scale growth.

These degradation models are not in themselves sufficient to enable through life performance simulation, as in a full stack there are significant variations in temperature and local current density, meaning different areas of the cell will be degrading at different rates. In addition, because of performance degradation through life, significant changes in the local temperature and current density distribution may occur, and the stack will often generate more heat meaning the air flow and/ or inlet temperature will need to change to maintain the nominal stack temperature.

To allow simulation of these effects, a full multiphysics stack model has been developed using COMSOL Multiphysics, incorporating fluid dynamics, heat transfer, electrochemical and heterogeneous chemical reactions. The electrochemical model at start of life is calibrated from extensive experimental performance mapping using coupon cells with high resolution AC impedance spectroscopy, and the resulting full multiphysics stack model validated against test data from real stacks.

A dynamic solver has then been applied to the multiphysics model applying the models of cell degradation to be applied to a full stack, including changing the air flow through life to maintain a constant nominal stack temperature. The model has been validated against through-life performance tests. This is a powerful tool which allows rapid evaluation of the likely impact of operating a stack in a condition other than ones in which extensive test data already exist.

Introduction

A considerable amount of work has been undertaken over the last few years to understand the performance degradation mechanisms of the Ceres Power metal-supported SteelCell[®] technology. The approach adopted has been broadly modelled on the Japanese NEDO project [1,2], although work has largely been undertaken internally at Ceres Power and not published.

The conclusions of that work to date are that Ceres technology is subject to similar performance degradation mechanisms to those widely reported in the literature for SOFC technology generally, and in the current generation of technology there are no technology-specific degradation mechanisms; those which have been identified in the past have been addressed by design changes to the cell/stack. Issues with substrate corrosion which have been widely reported for other metal-supported designs are not present in the SteelCell design. As reported elsewhere [3], Ceres technology is highly resistant to REDOX and thermal cycling by comparison with other SOFC designs due primarily to the inherent mechanical robustness of the metal supported design and the low operating temperature (<650°C). Also, primarily because of the low operating temperature performance degradation due to microstructural changes in the anode is negligible.

The latest V5 generation of SteelCell[®] technology has been demonstrated to have sufficiently low performance degradation for predicted lifetime to not be a limiting factor on commercialization, with experimental verification up to 27kh on a single stack, and multiple stacks at 20-25kh. The work described in this paper is focused on accelerated validation of operation under different operating conditions and identification of scope for future improvements, as the technology is already sufficiently robust and reliable for commercialization

As with most fuel cell developers, Ceres Power makes extensive use of AC impedance spectroscopy (ACIS) to characterize the breakdown of cell resistance and how it changes over time. Resistance contributions are broadly separated into ohmic resistances (non frequency-dependent) and frequency dependent polarization resistances. The main causes of performance degradation identified in SteelCell technology are.

- Ohmic resistance degradation (cathode current collection resistance degradation, electrolyte ionic conductivity degradation and anode-substrate interfacial resistance degradation primarily).
- Anode-side polarization resistance degradation through sulphur poisoning of internal steam reforming (the anode electrochemical reaction is fairly sulphur tolerant, as has been reported elsewhere [4] for Ni/CGO-based anodes).
- Cathode polarization resistance degradation through strontium segregation and poisoning by sulphur dioxide and chromium.

Mathematical models have been generated for resistance degradation as a function of time, current density and temperature based on long-duration short (17-layer) stack tests which readily allow ACIS measurements to be performed regularly on all layers, and are relatively isothermal. The functions chosen can be extrapolated to much longer test durations, with increasing uncertainty the further the functions are extrapolated beyond the experimental data on which they were calibrated.

A challenge common to the development of most fuel cell systems for stationary power generation is that the design life of the system is typically 60-100kh, which is commercially

impractical to verify experimentally within an acceptable timescale, so lifetime prediction inevitably involves a significant degree of extrapolation of data.

A further challenge related to lifetime prediction on full-size stacks operating in systems is that as the stack performance degrades, the operating voltage of the stack falls increasing the internal heat generation. To maintain the stack at its desired operating temperature, this needs to be compensated for by either increasing the cathode air flow or increasing the temperature gradient across the stack. Both control reactions will potentially change the internal temperature and current density distribution within the stack, and the degradation rate assuming the local resistance degradation rate varies with local temperature and current density. In addition, changing the cooling air flow through the stack has an impact on the net power output of a system by changing the parasitic power demand from the air blower, which potentially means the net performance loss from stack degradation is greater than the loss of stack power output alone.

It has also been established that polarization resistance degradation mechanisms related to poisoning/strontium depletion do not affect the cell uniformly, but preferentially affect the area of the electrodes nearest the air/fuel inlets first, gradually moving along the direction of gas flow with time as the electrodes become saturated with poison. This observation is in line with reports in the literature [5] in other SOFCs about the effect of sulphur on perovskite cathodes. This means that electrode degradation is not spatially uniform, but forms a moving front with the performance degradation being much greater at the inlet region of the cell. This again will distort the temperature and current density profile within the stack with time. Modeling and experimental testing has however demonstrated that provided the specified requirements for reactant feed quality are maintained these mechanisms should not be life-limiting.

The implication of spatially-dependent cell performance degradation is that a high-resolution mathematical model is required to predict through life performance, capturing most of the physics occurring within the stack both at start-of-life and through life. This is particularly useful for screening new stack designs and/or making predictions about the implications of changing the stack operating boundary conditions on degradation.

1. Scientific Approach

A high resolution multiphysics model of a Ceres Power stack has been developed using the COMSOL Multiphysics simulation package. The model uses a spatially averaged approach in the active volume of the stack to avoid computationally prohibitive simulation of the gas flows, heat flows and electrochemistry of each individual layer of a large stack, whilst still producing physically realistic predictions of the internal temperature and cell voltage profiles.

The model can be run at various levels of resolution between 'box model' where the active area of the stack is treated as a box with adiabatic thermal boundaries, and full simulation involving the actual stack geometry, full fluid dynamics in the manifolds and heat transfer through the stack walls. The full set of physics/chemistry simulated by the model is listed below.

- Turbulent computational fluid dynamics of the air and fuel flows in the manifolds.
- Porous media simulation of the fluid dynamics within the active area of the stack.
- Local current density.

- Local cell resistance.
- Local heat release due to the electrochemical reaction
- Local heat absorption due to the internal steam reforming reaction, with a kinetic model.
- Local gas composition in the air and fuel channels.
- Heat transfer between the air and fuel and the solid components of the stack.
- Heat transfer through conduction within the solid components of the stack.
- Heat transfer between the stack walls and the surroundings.

Figure 1: Example multiphysics simulation of a 17- layer short stack in a furnace showing 3D temperature profile. The stack is symmetrical along its centerline so only half the stack is meshed.

Figure 2: Example multiphysics simulation of a 250-layer 5kW stack surrounded by thermal insulation showing 3D temperature profile.

The electrochemistry model incorporated into the multiphysics model is calibrated from numerous button-cell measurements of the area-specific resistance (ASR) of the cell as a function of temperature, current density and hydrogen/oxygen partial pressures. The use of button cell measurements means the intrinsic cell performance can be measured independent of reactant utilization and temperature effects present in a stack.

The kinetics of internal steam reforming and the water-gas shift reaction have also been calibrated from experimental data.

The multiphysics models have been extensively validated at start-of-life against heavily instrumented experimental stacks, so there is good confidence in the accuracy of model predictions.

The initial multiphysics model is essentially a steady-state model. To simulate degradation some degree of dynamic modelling is required. An issue arises in that a degradation simulation requires being able to simulate the entire operating life of the stack in a reasonable computation time, and thus the model needs to be able run at thousands of times faster than real time. As many of the processes within the stack have very fast dynamics which would be impossible to simulate whilst also simulating tens-of-thousands of hours of operation, these have essentially been treated as instantaneous.

The only equations with a time dependent term are the heat balance of the solid parts of the stack and the equations governing degradation. In addition, to be realistic, it is necessary to modify the stack boundary conditions through simulated time to counteract the effect of increased heat release as the stack degrades to maintain a constant temperature. A simulated control loop using proportional control, with a tolerance band to limit the frequency of control interventions, has been implemented to achieve this. This approach has been shown to achieve acceptably stable simulated stack temperatures as a function of time whilst allowing practical simulation of 60kh of 5kW stack operation within a few days of CPU time.

Ohmic resistance degradation is simulated using an empirical model calibrated from multiple short stack tests giving ohmic resistance change as a function of temperature, current density and time.

Polarization resistance degradation through electrode poisoning is simulated by a moving front which progresses along the active cell area with time as the electrode becomes deactivated, at a rate calibrated from experimental measurements of cathode and steam reforming degradation as a function of temperature, reactant flow and poison concentration.

2. Results and Discussion

Figure 3 shows the predicted ohmic resistance degradation (in arbitrary units) as a function of time, temperature and current density over a range of 166-255 mAcm⁻², calibrated from experimental measurements for up to 25kh. Note that degradation follows a parabolic pattern, and long-term degradation rates are very low.

Figure 3: Predicted normalized ohmic resistance degradation as a function of temperature and current extrapolated to 80kh

Figure 4: Model output for a 1kW-type short stack simulation showing predicted local temperature and ASR at start of life (top) and after 10kh of operation (bottom) due to ohmic resistance degradation.

Figure 5: Predicted change in local ASR due to ohmic resistance degradation in middle cell of 5kW stack between start of life (left) and 60kh of operation (right).

Figure 4 shows the predicted change in local ASR and temperature for a 1kW-type short stack over 10kh of operation, applying the ohmic resistance degradation model shown in Figure 3.

Figure 5 shows the equivalent predicted change in local ASR due to ohmic resistance degradation in a 5kW stack over 60kh of operation. In both Figure 4 and Figure 5 the same color scale has been used for both initial and degraded plots, with the values and geometric detail of the 5kW stack obscured for reasons of commercial confidentiality.

Figure 6: Predicted voltage degradation for a short stack with only ohmic resistance degradation (blue line) or ohmic resistance degradation and highly accelerated internal steam reforming poisoning due to H₂S.

Figure 7: Experimental voltage degradation of a short stack with the equivalent level of H₂S in the fuel as the simulation.

Figure 6 shows the predicted effect of H₂S poisoning progressively deactivating the internal steam reforming of methane in a highly accelerated test where the H₂S concentration in the feed was well above the allowable limit for continuous operation. The blue line shows the predicted effect of ohmic resistance degradation only (the same data as shown in Figure 5), and ohmic resistance degradation with the addition of sulphur poisoning of the internal reforming reaction (orange line). The important point to note is that sulphur poisoning of the steam reforming reaction results in rapid initial degradation as the reforming kinetics are poisoned as a moving front along the fuel flow path of the cell. After around 4kh the degradation rate stabilizes as an equilibrium between the H₂S in the

fuel and surface coverage on the catalyst is achieved, provided the H₂S concentration is low enough.

Figure 7 shows the equivalent experimental data at the same H₂S concentration in the fuel as the simulation in Figure 6. Note that it has been verified that poisoning is almost exclusively due to loss of internal steam reforming, as switching the fuel feed to the stack from reformat to hydrogen/steam whilst maintaining the same concentration of H₂S almost completely reverses the performance degradation, showing that the electrochemical reaction is largely unaffected.

3. Conclusions

An extensive program of work has identified the major performance degradation mechanisms in Ceres Power SteelCell[®] technology, which are broadly similar to other SOFC technologies. The most recent version 5 release of the technology, which is now in commercial production shows intrinsic performance degradation compatible with an 80kh operating life. Mathematical models of the performance degradation associated with the known degradation mechanisms

An advanced multiphysics model of Ceres stacks has been developed in COMSOL Multiphysics, and extensively validated against experimental data at start-of-life for several different stack variants.

Mathematical models of the main degradation mechanisms have been incorporated into the stack multiphysics model, and a dynamic solver has been developed which allows the stack temperature to be controlled by adjusting the cathode air flow as the heat release increases over simulated time due to degradation. This solver runs at up to 1000 times real-time, and allows simulation of the entire operating life of the stack in a few days CPU time. This allows the simulation of through-life stack performance under a variety of operating conditions, and allows the likely lifetime impact of stack design changes or changes in operating conditions to be rapidly evaluated, without the need for an expensive and time-consuming experimental validation program.

The lifetime degradation model is a valuable tool which Ceres can use to accelerate design and market launch of products utilizing SteelCell[®] technology for multiple customers with differing requirements and system architectures.

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